
MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR CONTROLLER PLACEMENT IN SOFTWARE DEFINE NETWORK FOR MITIGATING DISTRIBUTED DENIAL OF SERVICE ATTACKS

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ABSTRACT

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) has revolutionized network management by introducing programmability, centralized control, and cost-effective solutions compared to traditional networking architectures. However, as SDN deployments scale to larger, more complex networks, challenges such as controller placement, reliability, and resilience against Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks become critical. The Controller Placement Problem (CPP) in SDN focuses on optimal controller allocation to minimize latency, enhance fault tolerance, and mitigate DDoS vulnerabilities. In this research, we propose a mathematical model for the CPP that simultaneously addresses these objectives, aiming to establish an efficient multi-controller setup that strengthens network performance and security. The model leverages a hybrid approach combining Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) and Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MOPSO) to solve this NP-hard problem by optimizing controller placement dynamically. The model will effectively improve latency, fault tolerance, and DDoS attack resilience, contributing to a robust and scalable SDN architecture capable of supporting diverse applications in dynamic network environments.

Keywords: *Software define network, performance factors, mathematical models, controller placement problems.*

INTRODUCTION

Software-defined networking (SDN) has gained prominence around the world because it is a programmable, cost-effective, agile, and centralized networking architecture compared to traditional systems that are more complicated and difficult to manage (Haque, Tan, Yusoff, Nisar, Kwang, et al., 2021; Liao et al., 2021). SDN decouples network control from dedicated network devices to form the control plane that uses standardized

interfaces to collect the runtime statistics, assemble a global network view from the statistics, and based on this view enable optimization applications. The core of the SDN architecture is the controller that mediates between clients and resources to deliver services (Alexandropoulos et al., 2019; Hasan et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2021; Lu et al., 2019; Okwu & Tartibu, 2021). This makes the control plane the perfect place to manage the unprecedented increased devices, data, and applications in widely various networking scenarios (Ahmad, 2020). SDN provides a visible, adaptable, and programmable layered network architecture that is capable of dealing with the continuously increasing network complexity (Haque, Tan, Yusoff, Nisar, Lee, et al., 2021).

The control plane of SDN can consist of one controller (the centralized control plane) or multiple cooperating controllers (the distributed control plane). A centralized control plane usually cannot efficiently provide flow forwarding for a large-scaled network because each new flow in the network has to involve the controller to set up forwarding rules at the involved switches (Hasan et al., 2020; F. Hu et al., 2014; Malik et al., 2020; Sufiev et al., 2019). Also, the extra workload added by collecting runtime statistics, the long propagation delay between a controller and its switches, and the longer flow forwarding procedure triggered by some security applications that force each flow in the network to be forwarded back to the control plane for security analysis can further increase the delay of the control plane in forwarding new flows of a network (El Kamel & Youssef, 2020; Liao et al., 2021). Furthermore, the centralized control plane is confronted with single point of failure issue, which decreases the scalability and availability of a network (Hussein et al., 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021). The shortcoming of this structure is that the centralized controller is vulnerable to an attacker generating spoofed packets to infiltrate the central controller. Among all attacks, distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks is among the most serious, generating huge amounts of artificial traffic to the SDN central controller and hampering its ability to provide services to legitimate clients (Gadallah et al., 2021).

The central controller has the processing capability and responsibility for directing the flow of data packets. By sending massive numbers of spoofed packets not found in current flow tables, the DDoS attacker can overload the central controller, which is unable to cope with the sudden influx of excessive fake packets, resulting in central controller malfunction. If the central controller becomes the victim of a DDoS attack, all switches

connected to that central controller will malfunction and disrupt SDN services for legitimate users (Mladenov & Iliev, 2020). By having multiple cooperating controllers in the control plane and carefully locating them over the whole network, SDN system can provide efficient flow management as well as enable various network applications over the whole network and curtail security challenges (Liao et al., 2021). In large-scale networks such as smart greenhouse with multiple domains, several controllers can be placed at different locations and assigned to monitor and control switches in each domain to enhance the network quality of service (QoS), traffic engineering, routing, fast failover, while ensuring that all controllers have the same global network view (Al-sharif et al., 2019; Aly et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2019a; Isong et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2021; Ramya & Manoharan, 2019). Consequently, the overall network performance can significantly increase due to effective load distribution among different controllers.

Also, the overall reliability increases as the failure of one controller do not inhibit the network operations, making the network more efficient and scalable (Isong et al., 2020; A Jalili & Keshtgari, 2020). Despite these benefits, multiple controllers also bring about several challenges known as controller placement problem (CPP) (Das et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2019, 2019; Isong et al., 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Lin et al., 2021; A. K. Singh et al., 2020). For instance, to ensure network scalability, it is insufficient to merely increase the number of controllers or randomly placing the controllers anywhere as a satisfactory performance can't be achieved. This means multiple controllers have to be properly placed in appropriate locations to meet several requirements and this action involved network partitioning (Bhujel et al., 2020; Isong et al., 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021). Nevertheless, partitioning the network into multiple control domains to achieve good network performance can introduce several challenges than anticipated in terms of reliability, load balancing, latency, fault tolerance, computation time, and threat mitigation (Isong et al., 2020; A Jalili & Keshtgari, 2020; Liao et al., 2021). It is against this backdrop that network engineers are faced with the CPP conundrum, prompting the search for answers to critical questions such as how to identify a minimum number of controllers, how to partition the network, where to locate each controller, and how to allocate controllers to switches. Seeking answers to these critical questions make multiple controllers' deployment for large-scale network management and its policies enforcement an important

research area (Isong et al., 2020; A Jalili & Keshtgari, 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Liao et al., 2021).

Thus, CPP is aimed at finding the optimal location of the SDN controllers in a manner that achieves various defined objectives such as latency minimization, load balancing, fault tolerance maximization, energy efficiency, and enhanced reliability. These defined objectives are critical to SDN's network performance (Das et al., 2020; Firouz et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2019, 2019; Isong et al., 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Lin et al., 2021; A. K. Singh et al., 2020). Therefore, careful planning and estimation of the optimal location allocation of the number of controllers are critical to reaping the benefits of CPP in SDN network. SDN emerged as a potential solution to the challenges faced in traditional networks, and its application in wireless sensor network (WSN). This new networking model was designed to address the inherent challenges and complexities associated with WSN and promote flexibility, latent efficiency, and innovations (Isong et al., 2020; Kobo et al., 2019). The challenges include energy inefficiency, network management, and configuration, scalability, security threats, routing, mobility as well as localization. In the perspective of security, to effectively utilize the services of the SDN, the CPP is equally important like the SDN. Some placements are achieved statically, others are realized dynamically (Isong et al., 2020). Hence, an SDN based CPP will require dynamic placement and virtualization. Dynamic controller placement methods could be adopted to ensure effectiveness in the CPP strategy that can be used to mitigate DDoS attacks. CPP was first considered as a non-deterministic polynomial (NP)-hard problem and is similar to the facility location problem (Huang et al., 2019, 2019; Isong et al., 2020; A Jalili & Keshtgari, 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021). Solving CPP is challenging and requires proper planning and good decision making to achieve optimal location and satisfactory results (Isong et al., 2020). For multiple controllers' placement, several factors influence the SDN performance such as reliability, controller load balancing, latency, operational costs, fault tolerance, threat mitigation and response time of events (Eliyan & Di Pietro, 2021; Haque, Tan, Yusoff, Nisar, Kwang, et al., 2021; Hasan et al., 2020; Isong et al., 2020; A Jalili & Keshtgari, 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Yunyan Li et al., 2019; Liao et al., 2021). Researchers working on CPP use one or more objectives to formulate the problem (Das et al., 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Lin et al., 2021; Sahoo, Sarkar, et al., 2017; A. K. Singh & Srivastava, 2018). The choice of an objective is primarily influenced by the resources one aspires to optimize.

However, there are certain performance objectives which cannot be optimized in isolation without conflicting with other performance parameters, hence the need for tradeoff between multi objective problems (Ghanbari et al., 2019; Kumari & Sairam, 2021). The performance parameter reliability enhances controller availability, while, reliable controller placement enhance security. Attackers can overload controller resources with DDoS flooding requests when the controller CPU and memory is overloaded, it will not be able to process incoming flows from legitimate sources, this degrades the performance of the entire network and affect the controller availability (Al-sharif et al., 2019; A Jalili & Keshtgari, 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Vangala et al., 2021). Due to the multi-objective nature of the CPP in SDN, it is very important to optimize both network parameters and security at the same time, due to the effect they have on each other. The aim of this research is to formulate mathematical model for controller placement problem that involves network parameters and security mitigation. One approach to minimize the effect of security attacks on SDN is reliable controller placement of multiple controllers, known as CPP (Das et al., 2020; Firouz et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2019, 2019; Isong et al., 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Yi Li et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2021; A. K. Singh et al., 2020). Multiple controllers ensure a switch is linked to several controllers to eliminate a single point of failure as experienced with a centralized controller (Al-sharif et al., 2019; Gadallah et al., 2021; Haque et al., 2020; Haque, Tan, Yusoff, Nisar, Kwang, et al., 2021; Isong et al., 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Tivig & Borcoci, 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recently, several approaches have been proposed and developed to solve SDN-based CPP and each approach has its own set of objectives which are either to minimize or maximize or both (Das et al., 2020; Firouz et al., 2021; Isong et al., 2020; Yi Li et al., 2020; A. K. Singh et al., 2020; Yoon et al., 2017). Existing approaches in terms of controller allocation and the optimal number of controllers has been classified as shown in Figure 2. 1. Figure 2.1 present a simple yet informative classification of CPP based on several factors or metrics that influence SDN performance and QoS as well as how such metrics are optimized (Isong et al., 2020).

Figure 2.1: Controller placement problem strategies (Isong et al., 2020; Kumari & Sairam, 2021)

As shown in Figure 2.1 reliability is an influencing factor in the CPP due to the criticality of message exchanges involving Switch to Controller (SC) and Controller to Controller (CC) in the SDN (Isong et al., 2020). Moreover, reliability involves measures set in place to ensure that in the event of failure, there is no single point of failure and the communication between controllers and switches is not interrupted. This is the basis of its criticality in SDN-based CPP and several approaches exist to improving reliability such as multiple controllers, multiple control-path, and minimizing control-path (Ashrafi et al., 2020; Eliyan & Di Pietro, 2021; Haque, Tan, Yusoff, Nisar, Kwang, et al., 2021; Haque, Tan, Yusoff, Nisar, Lee, et al., 2021; Hossein & Watts, 2019; Isong et al., 2020; J. Lu et al., 2019a; Mohanty et al., 2019). While the multiple control-path ensures that there exist at least two disjoint paths linking a controller and a switch, multiple controllers ensure a switch is linked to several controllers to eliminate a single point of failure as experienced with a centralized controller (Isong et al., 2020), which is an interest of this research. Moreover, minimizing control-path involves a reduction in the physical unit of the control-path, thereby improving reliability. These approaches are based on the probability of failure, ρ and Equation (2. 2) presents the formulation for multiple

controllers where $\rho(v, u)$ indicates control-path availability probability (Isong et al., 2020).

$$R_{mc} = \max \sum_{v \in V} (1 - \prod_{u \in U} (1 - p(v, u)))$$

Where $\rho(v, u)$ is given by:

$$\rho(v, u) = \prod_{t \in d(v, u)} (1 - p_t)$$

When multi-objectives are considered in the controller placement, though conflicting in nature, two or more metrics are considered (Das et al., 2020; Isong et al., 2020; A Jalili & Keshtgari, 2020; Khosroabadi et al., 2021; Kumari & Sairam, 2021; Lo et al., 2019; Manzoor et al., 2020; Rong et al., 2020). Although, there is no fixed number of metrics to optimize, it all depends on the researcher's objective. In this case, the problem is formulated as shown in Equation 2.3 (Isong et al., 2020; J. Lu et al., 2019a).

$$M_{ob} = \max [Parameter1, Parameter2, Parameter3 \dots \dots]$$

Therefore, to satisfy each performance metric or group of metrics, several algorithms or approaches have been proposed and utilized. (Mohanty et al., 2019) proposed mathematical model for reliable controller placement for multi objective problem, which minimizes the total cost of the network considering the capacity constraint of the controller. The simulated results show a good performance at different reliability levels. However, it did not consider fault tolerance and threat mitigation. Also, (Ramya & Manoharan, 2019) adapt a concept from graph theory to estimate number of controllers and its placements. The controller placement method identifies the articulation points in network and places controller at articulation points. The simulated results obtained validate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. However, it did not address primary controller placement problem with performance metrics and DDoS attacks mitigation. (Haque, Tan, Yusoff, Nisar, Kwang, et al., 2021) propose a mathematical model for planning the deployment of SDN smart backup controllers (SBCs) to preserve service in the presence of DDoS attacks. Simulated results of the proposed model demonstrate that the model is useful in planning for SDN reliability in the presence of DDoS attacks while managing the overall cost. but this method does not consider optimizing trade-off between any of the performance factors of SDN such as latency, controller capacity, propagation delay, and energy consumption. Hence, the need for

development of mathematical model for multiple controller placement that will consider latency, fault tolerance and threat mitigation.

Formulation of the mathematical model

The formulation of mathematical model for controller placement problem is by minimizing latency, maximizing fault tolerance and minimizing DDoS Attacks is based on the following components:

1. Decision variables

Let.

- I. $C = \{c_1, c_2 \dots c_n\}$ represent the set of n controllers to be placed in the network.
- II. $S = \{s_1, s_2 \dots s_m\}$ represent the set of m switches in the SDN.
- III. $X = [x_{ij}]$ where $x_{ij} = 1$ if switch s_j is assigned to controller c_i and $x_{ij} = 0$ otherwise.
- IV. $Y = [y_i]$ where $y_i = 1$ if controller c_i is active (placed), and $y_i = 0$ otherwise.

2. Objective functions

The optimization problem aims to balance three objectives: This includes latency, fault tolerance, and DDoS attacks mitigation.

- i. Minimization
 - a. Latency

$$Z_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} L_{ij}$$

Where L_{ij} is the latency between controller c_i and switch s_j , depending on the network topology and link delays. This objective minimizes the total latency across all controller-switch connections.

- b. DDoS Attack Impact

$$Z_2 = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i D_i$$

Where D_i represent the vulnerability of controller c_i to DDoS attacks, been a function of the traffic load and security measures in place. The impact of DDoS attacks can be minimized by distributing controllers and enhancing their resilience. This objective minimizes the potential DDoS vulnerability by optimizing controller placement.

- ii. Maximization
 - a. Fault tolerance ensure that in case of controller failure, the network can still operate. It can be modeled using redundancy and the availability of backup controllers.

$$Z_3 = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} R_{ij}$$

Where R_{ij} is the redundancy factors between controller c_i and switch s_j , been a measure of alternative paths or backup controllers.

$$Z = Z_1 + Z_2 + Z_3$$

3. Constraints

The optimization problem is subject to several constraints.

i. Controller placement constraint

Each switch must be assigned to exactly one active controller:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$$

Connectivity constraint

Ensure that each switch is connected to a controller with acceptable latency by setting an upper bound L_{max} for the maximum acceptable latency.

$$x_{ij}L_{ij} \leq L_{max} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, n\},$$

$$\forall j \in \{1, \dots, m\} \quad (3.6)$$

ii. Redundancy constraints

Redundancy ensures that each switch has at least one backup controller, requiring that each switch is connected to at least two controllers (primary and backup):

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} \geq 2, \forall j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$$

Hybrid Algorithm

The hybrid algorithm combines NSGA-II for handling the multi-objective nature of the problem with MOPSO for efficient global exploitation:

a. NSGA-II optimizes the placement of controllers by evolving a population of solutions and sorting them based on non-dominance and crowding distance. This is achieved by

i. Crossover and Mutation: We define the crossover operator $C(x^a, x^b)$ and mutation operator $M(x)$ to generate new offspring from parents x^a and x^b .

$$x^{new} = M\left(C(x^a, x^b)\right)$$

ii. Fitness evaluation: Evaluate the fitness of each individual x using the objective functions in equation (3.1, 3.2 and 3.3)

ii. Selection and Ranking: Apply non-dominated sorting to rank the individuals based on pareto dominance using crowding distance to maintain diversity in the population.

a. MOPSO update the population using particles swarm optimization principles to enhance search space exploration, particularly for latency minimization and fault tolerance maximization using:

i. Particle position: Update the position x_i of each particle.

ii. Velocity: Update velocity v_i of each particle.

Using the standard PSO update rules.

$$v_i^{(t+1)} = w \cdot v_i^{(t)} + c_1 \cdot r_1 \cdot (p_i^{best} - x_i^{(t)}) + c_2 \cdot r_2 \cdot (g_i^{best} - x_i^{(t)}) \quad (3.9)$$

$$x_i^{(i+1)} = x_i^{(t)} + v_i^{(t+1)}$$

Where p_i^{best} and g_i^{best} are the personal and global best positions, ω is the inertia weight, and c_1, c_2 are acceleration coefficients. The formulated mathematical equation using equation 3.4

$$Z_{min} = Z$$

Therefore,

$$Z_{min} = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} L_{ij} + \sum_{i=1}^n y_i D_i -$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} R_{ij}$$

Subject to:

- a. $\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall j$
- b. $x_{ij} L_{ij} \leq L_{max} \quad \forall i, j$
- c. $\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij} \geq 2 \quad \forall i$
- d. $x_{ij}, y_i \in \{0, 1\}$

Nonnegativity

- a. $x_{ij} \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, n; j = 1, \dots, m$

This provides a mathematical foundation for implementing a hybrid NSGA-II and MOPSO algorithm to optimize controller placement with the given objectives and constraints.

CONCLUSION

Software-defined networking (SDN) offers a transformative approach to modern network architecture, prioritizing programmability, cost-effectiveness, and centralized control. However, as SDN scales to accommodate diverse applications and larger network environments, the need for robust controller placement strategies becomes crucial. The centralization of the SDN controller introduces potential vulnerabilities, particularly against Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, which can severely impact network stability and performance. Addressing these challenges, particularly in large-scale networks, has led to the development of the Controller Placement Problem (CPP), which seeks optimal controller locations to balance multiple objectives—such as reducing latency, enhancing fault tolerance, and mitigating security risks.

This research aims to address the CPP through a mathematical model that integrates multi-objective optimization with dynamic controller placement to improve SDN network resilience and performance. By leveraging hybrid algorithms, specifically a combination of NSGA-II and MOPSO, this study proposes an efficient method to determine the optimal controller placement strategy, balancing network latency, fault tolerance, and security concerns. This approach contributes significantly to the goal of ensuring a scalable, reliable, and secure SDN infrastructure capable of meeting the demands of future network applications.

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